

IMPORTANCE OF INTRODUCED MEDICINAL TREES

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Abstract: When plants are introduced from their natural range to new areas, the viability of the species (varieties) and the valuable economic characteristics that are the goal of the introduction are improved: fruit yield increases, phytomass increases, resistance to various environmental factors, diseases, and pests increases.

Key words: area, introduction, variety, viability, farm mark, phytomass, genetics

Annotatsiya: O‘simliklar tabiiy arealdan yangi hududlarga Introduksiya qilinganda turlar (navlar)ning hayotchanligi va Introduksiyaning maqsadi bo‘lgan qimmatli xo‘jalik‘belgilarining yaxshilanishi yuz beradi: meva hosildorligi ko‘tariladi, fitomassa ko‘payadi, muhitning turli omillariga, kasallik, zararkunandalarga chi-damliligi ortadi

Kalit so‘zlar: areal, introduksiya, nav, hayotchanlik, xo‘jalik belgisi, fitomassa, genetika

Аннотация: При интродукции растений из естественного ареала в новые районы улучшаются жизнеспособность видов (сортов) и ценные хозяйственные признаки, являющиеся целью интродукции: повышается урожайность плодов, увеличивается фитомасса, устойчивость к различным факторам внешней среды, болезней и вредителей увеличивается.

Ключевые слова: интродукции, ареала, хозяйственные хозяйственные, фитомасса, устойчивость, болезней, вредителей.

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Introduction of plants helps not only to increase their valuable traits for the economy, but also to expand their distribution area and to create new populations within the species as a result of adaptation to new environmental conditions over the years. Introduction from "home centers" has expanded the range of plants to a certain extent, and in this regard, the connection of some plants with the primary centers is broken. For example, the homeland of ground nut is Shim, Argentina, but now peanuts are mostly grown in equatorial Africa. The homeland of potatoes is South America, but, today it is a staple food product in many countries of the world.

In order to introduce various plants and collecting materials scientific expeditions are carried out to the centers of primary and secondary origin of cultivated plants. For example, scientific expeditions were organized to Mexico in 1975, Peru in 1984, Sri Lanka, India, China in 1989-90, and Australia in 1997 under the leadership of Academician A. Abdullaev at the Institute of Experimental Plant Biology of Uzbekistan FA. Plant introduction and subsequent acclimatization are carried out in botanical and breeding institutions.

In our country, in the 30s of the 20th century, in the newly established scientific organizations, on the basis of a specific scientific plan, the collection and introduction of various types of world cultivated and wild plants began. To date, collections of various crops based on introduced and local varieties have been established at the Institute of Plant Experimental Biology, Botanical Research Institute, and Botanical Garden of Uzbekistan.

Today, when scientific cooperation between the countries of the world has expanded, the task of introduction is to attract plants to new countries on a scientific basis and to enrich the existing crop varieties with modern industrial varieties. The introduction of plants with different life forms will have a different

purpose. For example, deciduous, coniferous, evergreen and deciduous plants are selected for landscape trees and shrubs. Oak (oak), chestnut, maple, acacia, white birch, willow, poplar, cypress, white pine, boxwood, hawthorn, juniper are planted on avenues, streets, ponds and lakes. Plants such as vines, ivy, roses, and sirens are more planted around sheds and porches. In recent years, ornamental trees and shrubs have been introduced and acclimatized to the above-mentioned and noteworthy places of our Republic from different countries of the world. During the introduction, special attention is paid not only to the beauty of plants, but also to their medicinal properties.

useful birch-Betulaceae

Useful birch (Betulaceae) is widely used for the beauty of its crown and open leaves, its pollen transportability in beekeeping, its diuretic, bactericidal, wound-healing and antipyretic properties, and the oil extract from birch buds is used as a dermatological agent, and its juice has the property of purifying the blood.[5]].

Red oak - quercus rubra

Red oak - quercus rubra is distinguished by its phytoncide release and as a landscape tree, it is planted as an ornamental plant in streets, avenues and parks. Due to its resistance to frost, resistance to cold and pests, it can adapt to soil conditions in different environments and is spread over a wide area. Red oak is used in medicine, for woodworking and furniture making, because it produces unique fruits [5].

Ginkgo biloba

Ginkgo leaves are recognized and appreciated in many countries of the world for their uniqueness. They are used in the production of expensive medicines, as well as in folk medicine. At home, doctors prepare alcohol and water infusions, herbal teas, which are much cheaper for people than various imported medicines.

False chestnut - Aesculus hippocastanum

Representatives of this family are tree plants.

All species are characterized by being extremely beautiful. Therefore, they have great importance in landscaping works. It is recommended to plant all kinds of false chestnuts on city streets. A lot of fake flowers are grown in the streets and parks of Tashkent city.

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